

Conversational Chat-Bot Application

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Abstract

In today's world anxiety, depression, loneliness is increasing day by day due to less interaction with outside world and everyday amount of time people going to spend on smart technology device is increasing day by day. The objective of paper is show-case the design and implementation of a conversational chatbot which we have developed. This chatbot provides various features for the user such as providing a conversational feature.

The utilization of chatbots advanced quickly in various fields lately, including Schooling, Medical services, Social Legacy, and Amusement. In this paper, we first present the technologies which are helpful for chatbot development and how they are affecting our chatbot development. Then we are going to show to flow of our chatbot and various features which can be added in the chatbot.

Keywords

Rasa Core, Rasa Nlu, Machine Learning, Chatbot, Natural Language Processing, Sentimental Analysis.

1. Introduction

Trouble in seeing a specialist, long lining time, and burden of causing arrangements to have for some

time been obstacles confronting patients when they attempt to get to essential consideration administrations.[1] To settle these difficulties,

legislatures and medical services suppliers all over the planet are putting resources into new techniques that work with more powerful utilization of assets to fulfill needs.

It will be going to act as another human being to be able to understand the user problems and their various problems for example if a person is feeling happy or sad. [2] This chatbot will be providing the user with Jokes/Videos which indeed going to help the user to have a better mental health.

Even though our chatbot is itself a tech product but this conversational chatbot not only just encourage people to go out and enjoy with outside world but also will be going to help out the society to overcome the problems faced and going to help them to improve on it.

Conversational specialists, otherwise called chatbots, are PC programs intended to reenact human text or verbal discussions.[2] They are progressively utilized in a scope of fields, including medical services.[3] By empowering better availability, personalization, and proficiency, conversational specialists can possibly work on understanding consideration.[4]

Man-made consciousness (artificial intelligence) is progressively being utilized in medical care. Here, man-made intelligence based chatbot frameworks can go about as computerized conversational specialists, equipped for advancing wellbeing, giving training, and possibly inciting conduct change.[4] Investigating the inspiration to utilize wellbeing chatbots is expected to foresee take-up; in any case, barely any examinations to date have investigated their worthiness.[5] This examination meant to investigate members' eagerness to draw in with artificial intelligence drove wellbeing chatbots.

2. Literature review

Anxiety and depression rates are at an unequaled high. Cell phone based emotional wellness chatbots can help specialists supplanting a portion of the expensive human-based connection giving an exceptional chance to extend the accessibility and nature of psychological well-being mediation while giving an elective way to deal with fill the genuinely necessary taking care of self-care gap.[6]

For what reason do clients utilize chatbots? Chatbots appear to hold enormous commitment for giving clients fast and helpful help answering explicitly to their inquiries.[7] The most incessant inspiration for chatbot clients is viewed as efficiency, while different thought processes are diversion, social factors, and contact with curiosity [8]. Notwithstanding, to adjust the inspirations referenced over, a chatbot ought to be inherent a way that goes about as an instrument, a toy, and a companion simultaneously

One of the main causes of the burden of disease worldwide is mental health problems [9]. In the UK, mental health constitutes 28% of the total burden of disease, compared to 16% each for cancer and heart disease [10]. Statistics now show that one in four people in the UK will experience a mental health problem in any given year [11].

3. Essential Concepts

Chat bots in order to be user-friendly have to provide precise information as attention spans among users have decreased alarming over the previous decade. In order to do this NLP helps as it provides exact answers. Python is a high-level programming language which will be used for the implementation of the Conversational Chatbot.[12] Its syntax is similar to pseudo code of other high-level languages such as Java or C++, this is one of the main reasons it is the most trending language among developers as it is easy to understand and drastically reduces development time and it can seamlessly integrate with tens and hundreds of libraries making it a go to platform for projects involving machine learning,

natural language processing or any project involving data analytics. Since it is free and over source along with being portable in terms of operating system (Linux/Windows/Mac).

4. Methodology

Utilization of Sentiment Analysis

One of the primary features of our conversational chatbot will be its potential to analyze sentiment of the user on the basis of answer of the user to any particular question throughout the conversation, once the sentiment has been analyzed (happy, sad, anxious, angry). Then the chatbot moves ahead with the conversation accordingly

For ex: *A user is analyzed to be sad based on his/her responses then the chatbot will try and elevate the mood by showing funny images of humans or cute photos of cats or dogs to make the user a little less sad.*

This allows the our chatbot to have the potential from moving away from information retrieval to providing technical self-service to the user and also it can be modified into becoming a digital health intervention as the task of providing quality medical healthcare to an increasing population becomes ever so difficult.[13]

The use of mixed methods allowed new concepts to be tested in the online survey, as the qualitative analysis of views on AI-led chatbots fed into the quantitative arm of the study.[14] In addition, the demonstration of the popular chatbot and the opportunity for participants to directly interact with it likely strengthen the validity of the findings, as the explored views were not purely hypothetical but based on experience during the study.[15] The qualitative sub-study also informed the development of the exploratory survey, increasing its reliability, although a further investigation into the development of measurement tool is needed. Nevertheless, the survey responses were mainly drawn from students and internet users, in particular, a young and educated cohort that might not be representative of the population that might be asked to use health chatbots.[14]

Ngrok

Using the third-party software ngrok as a forwarding server, he can forward the external request to the port you specify.[15] The background principle is to connect to the ngrok cloud server, expose the address specified by your machine, and then use ngrok.[16] A bunch of public URLs to access content. His strengths are quick and also provide https services that make you safer to use.[17] Ngrok can use the external network to access the website

deployed on the local server.[16] Through ngrok, you can quickly establish an Internet-connectable web server, so that the test environment of the local computer can be directly connected to the outside for testing and debugging. [17]

Rasa Core and Rasa NLU Machine Learning Frameworks

Rasa Open Source is an open-source conversational AI platform that allows you to understand and hold conversations, and connect to messaging channels and third party systems through a set of APIs.[19] It supplies the building blocks for creating virtual (digital) assistants or chatbots.[20]

```

85 ## intent:mood_unhappy
86 - my day was horrible
87 - I am sad
88 - I don't feel very well
89 - I am disappointed
90 - super sad
91 - I'm so sad
92 - sad
93 - very sad
94 - unhappy
95 - bad
96 - very bad
97 - awful
98 - terrible
99 - not so good
100 - not very good
101 - extremely sad
102 - so sad
103
104 - Quite bad - can I get a cute picture of a [bird](group:birds), please?
105 - Really bad and only [doggo](group:shibes) pics and change that.
106 - Not good. The only thing that could make me feel better is a picture of a cute [kitten](group:cats).
107 - so sad. Only the picture of a [sussy](group:shibes) could make it better.
108 - I am very sad. I need a [cat](group:cats) picture.
109 - Extremely sad. Only the cute [doggo](group:shibes) pics can make me feel better.
110 - Bad. Please show me a [bird](group:birds) pic!
111 - Pretty bad to be honest. Can you show me a [sussy](group:shibes) picture to make me feel better?
112 - I'm sad
113 - in sad
114 - in sad
115 - I am sad
116 - in sad
  
```

Linking of Training Data to our NLU Model

```

1 ## intent:goodbye
2 - cu
3 - good by
4 - see you later
5 - good night
6 - good afternoon
7 - bye
8 - goodbye
9 - have a nice day
10 - see you around
11 - bye bye
12 - see you later
13 - bye
14 - y
15 - bye
16
17 ## intent:greet
18 - hey
19 - hello there
20 - hi
21 - hello there
22 - good morning
23 - good evening
24 - moin
25 - hey there
26 - let's go
27 - hey dude
28 - goodmorning
29 - goodevening
30 - good afternoon
31 - Hi
32 - Hello
33
34 ## intent:inform
35 - A [dog](group:shibes)
36 - [dog](group:shibes)
37 - [bird](group:birds)
38 - a [cat](group:cats)
39 - [cat](group:cats)
40 - a [bird](group:birds)
41 - of a [dog](group:shibes)
42 - of a [cat](group:cats)
43 - a [bird](group:birds), please
44 - a [dog](group:shibes), please
45 - a [dog](group:shibes)
46 - [dog](group:shibes)
47 - a [cat](group:cats)
48 - a [cat](group:cats)
49 - [dog](group:shibes)
50 - a [dog](group:shibes)
51 - [dog](group:shibes)
52 - a [cat](group:cats)
53
54 ## intent:mood_affirm
55 - yes
56 - Indeed
57 - of course
58 - that sounds good
59 - correct
60
61 ## intent:mood_deny
62 - no
63 - never
64 - I don't think so
65 - don't like that
66 - no way
67 - not really
  
```

5. Brief about Training Data

The following training data has fed into the program to create realistic conversations with potential users in order to create and enhance experience.

These are separated according to the four emotions that has been presented in the diagrammatic representation of our chatbot i.e., Happy, Sad, Anxious, Depressed.

6. Application

There are various applications of this conversational chat some are mentioned below:

Our conversational chatbot can be used in wide range of applications of healthcare as well as to have an impact on user mood.

Diagnosis: It helps in helping the user with a effective diagnosis on various healthcare issues such as Depression and Anxiety. [18]. Though the doctor's prescription is required but due to ease of use it can be accessed anywhere not worrying about to be present to be hospital, wait in long queues to get the consultancy.

7. Training Data

Training and Linking for Behavior

```

1 ## happy path
2 * greet
3 - utter_greet
4 * mood_great
5 - utter_happy
6 * mood_affirm
7 - utter_happy
8 * mood_affirm
9 - utter_goodbye
10
11 ## sad path 1
12 * greet
13 - utter_greet
14 * mood_unhappy
15 - utter_ask_picture
16 * inform("animal":"dog")
17 - action_retrieve_image
18 - utter_ask_picture
19 * mood_affirm
20 - utter_happy
21
22 ## sad path 2
23 * greet
24 - utter_greet
25 * mood_unhappy
26 - utter_ask_picture
27 * inform("group":"cat")
28 - action_retrieve_image
29 - utter_ask_picture
30 * mood_deny
31 - utter_goodbye
32
33 ## intent:mood_anxious
34 - I don't know what to do.
35 - I can not seem to think of a way out of this.
36 - I am clueless how to proceed.
37
38 ## intent: mood_depressed
39 - There is no end to my suffering
40 - Life is a hopeless repetition of failure.
41 - I can not do anything good.
42
43 ## Generated Story 8002354599375/25553
44 * greet
45 * mood_unhappy
46 - utter_ask_picture
47 * inform("group": "shibes")
48 - slot("group": "shibes")
49 - action_retrieve_image
50 - utter_ask_picture
51 * mood_unhappy
52 - utter_ask_picture
53 * inform("group": "shibes")
54 - slot("group": "shibes")
55 - action_retrieve_image
56 - utter_ask_picture
57 * mood_unhappy
58 - utter_ask_picture
59 * inform("group": "shibes")
60 - slot("group": "shibes")
61 - action_retrieve_image
62 - utter_ask_picture
63 * mood_unhappy
64 - utter_ask_picture
65 * inform("group": "shibes")
66 - slot("group": "shibes")
67 - action_retrieve_image
68 - utter_ask_picture
69 * mood_unhappy
70 - utter_ask_picture
71 * inform("group": "shibes")
72 - slot("group": "shibes")
73 - action_retrieve_image
74 - utter_ask_picture
75 * mood_unhappy
76 - utter_ask_picture
77 * inform("group": "shibes")
78 - slot("group": "shibes")
79 - action_retrieve_image
80 - utter_ask_picture
81 * mood_unhappy
82 - utter_ask_picture
  
```

Psychiatric treatment: Chatbots cover psychiatric treatments, for conversational therapy, deliver an objective appraisal or to identify harmful tendencies

Self-Diagnosis: Chatbots for self-determination is an effective method for informing patients as the primary point regarding contact even before they go to a medical services office [19]

Documentation: It can be used to provide processed documentation which can help the physicians to access the patient condition properly.

8. Features Comparison

Feature Comparison of our Conversational Chatbot		
Features	ChatBot	Telegram Bot
Text Message	Y	Y
Carousel	N	N
Button	Y	Y
Quick Reply	Y	N
Web View	Y	N
Group Chatbot	Y	Y
List	N	N
Audio	N	Y
Video	N	Y
GIF	Y	Y
Image	Y	Y
Document file	N	Y
Sentiment analysis	Y	N

9. Sentiment Prediction Accuracy

11. Chatbot User Growth

Table: Literature Review

YEAR	AUTHOR	PURPOSE	Methodology	CONCLUSION
2017	Gillian Cameron et al [20]	<i>Towards a Chatbot for digital counselling.</i>	Incremental Prototyping with a demo chatbot prepared using Emoji's and GIF and the final Version being a full web-based program for mental health for the entire world.[21]	Research has demonstrated that the clients have found chatbots "safe" and simple to converse with. Chatbots can make one more choice for clients who would rather not get face to face treatment, but there are numerous moral perspectives to consider.
2021	Arfan Ahmed et al [22]	<i>A review of mobile chatbot apps for anxiety and depression and their self-care features.[22]</i>	Conducting a review of available chatbots on Google Play Store(android) and Apple Store(iOS).[22] Following of guidelines set under Proffered Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) group.[22] Including Data Extraction, Data Synthesis and a Quality assessment framework.[23]	Albeit numerous psychological wellness problem related applications exist, just 11 chatbots were found related that met the incorporation standards and were accessible on Google Play Store and Apple Store. They all met most of the mHONCode principles and were built with various self-care interventions and other types of interventions, such as CBT and mindfulness.[22]
2020	Qiming Bao et al [24]	<i>HHH: An Online Medical Chatbot System based on Knowledge Graph and Hierarchical Bi-Directional Attention</i>	Application of Knowledge graph. Application of Hierarchical Bi-Directional Attention Text Representation and Similarity Model	The capability of chatbot innovations to assume a considerably more huge part in the clinical space. For instance, a product chatbot can be sent in reality to become home medical services robots or clinic clinical request robots. According to the application perspective, the paper just thought to be the single-turn responsive instrument. [25] A significant future heading is to add client profiles into the framework and give a more exact clinical collaborator to every particular client. Plus, we can consolidate the information mining strategy and foresee the possible sicknesses in a locale of the populace.

Table: Literature Review

YEAR	AUTHOR	PURPOSE	Methodology	CONCLUSION
2020	Prissadang Suta, Xi Lan, Biting Wu [26]	<i>An Overview of Machine Learning in Chatbots.</i>	The branches stemming from the center represent the main characteristics, current architectures and systems, machine learning approaches, and applications of chatbots. [27]	This can help researchers develop a better understanding of the current implementation techniques and usages of chatbots.[26] This is important because chat is becoming more and more popular as an intelligent virtual assistant, especially for customer service and personal use in the industry.[27]
2018	Michael McTear [28]	<i>Conversational Modelling for Chatbots current approaches and Future Directions</i>	This paper examines the conversation models of the main chatbot frameworks and assesses the extent to which they model important conversational phenomena such as follow-up questions, changes of topic, out-of-scope utterances, and other conversational phenomena. [29]	This paper shows that conversation is a complex system and we cannot rely on general concepts to design conversational interfaces.[29] Modelling the sequential mechanics of conversation is essential to make interactions with chatbots intuitive and natural.[28]
2019	Aditya Nrusimha Vaidyam [30]	<i>The aim of this review was to explore the current evidence for conversational agents or chatbots in the field of psychiatry and their role in screening, diagnosis, and treatment of mental illnesses.[30]</i>	A systematic literature search in June 2018 was conducted in PubMed, EmBase, PsycINFO, Cochrane, Web of Science, and IEEE Xplore.[30] Studies were included that involved a chatbot in a mental health setting focusing on populations with or at high risk of developing depression, anxiety, schizophrenia, bipolar, and substance abuse disorders.[31]	Early evidence for psychiatric use of chatbots is favorable.[31] To more fully examine the efficacy of dialogue findings, however, additional research with consistent results reporting is required given the variability of the examined studies.[32] Regardless, early evidence shows that with the proper approach and research, the mental health field could use conversational agents in psychiatric treatment.[33]

12. Conclusion

Using all the benefits of various technologies we now can conclude that these are the functionality which we gain from this conversational chatbot.[32] According to our research, Rasa Framework and sentiment analysis can be used to generate chatbot replies that are quite similar to those of a human. This would make it simpler for the user to interact with the chatbot. The major goals of this project are to create an algorithm that will be used to find responses to queries from users. By integrating emotional wellness screening instruments into a chatbot interface, the client can have a more intuitive and easier to understand insight.[33] Research has shown clients find chatbots "safe" and simple to converse with.

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